

Factors Influencing the Development of Athletes' Excellence

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ABSTRACT

The purposes of the research were to study the factors affecting the development of athletes' excellence and to figure out the guidelines for developing the athletes' excellence. The researcher collected the data by in-depth interviews and the questionnaire. The data analysis by descriptive report. The research found that physical fitness is the one of success indicator of athlete of all levels and sports. The factors of sports skill and technique are important for developing the athletes to excellent, especially the learning skill and technique since childhood, the development of sports skill and technique together with physical fitness and the learning skill and technique are continuously trained until it is habitual regularly. The factors of psychological fitness are important and absolutely necessary for the athlete development to excellence. The effective guidelines for developing the athletes' excellence in physical fitness, sports skill and technique, psychological fitness, body structure and sex hormone to success must work in the same direction, especially athletes, coaches, family are the most important stakeholder in the success of sport.

KEYWORDS: Development /Competency /Athletes Excellence

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I. INTRODUCTION

"Sport is an important part of the public's way in every sector. It is also an important mechanism for creating social and economic values of the country" [7]. According to the 20-year vision of Thailand, this aims to develop the sport of Thailand to have the same potential as a country that is a superpower in the sports industry. By the National Sports Development Plan, No. 6 (2017-2021) is a framework for operations [8]. Therefore, the development of athletes to excellence is an important national agenda that the government sector and related agencies should accelerate to develop athletes to excellence seriously and concretely [4]. The way to be a good solution to develop athletes to increase their work efficiency and higher potential at the international level is to use human resource management strategies or tools using basic competencies (Competency-based Human Resource Management) to be used in the development of athletes to have higher performance and achieve success in various competitions, until being able to further develop into a professional athlete [10]. Therefore, the use of competency methods in the development of athletes will be another way to help solve such human resource problems.

II. OBJECTIVE

1. To study factors affecting the development of athletes' performance to excellence
2. To study guidelines for the development of athletic performance to excellence.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The tools used to collect 2 sets of data are as follows:

1. Semi-structured interview for trainers Sports scientist Sports psychologist and kinesiologist. Which is an interview form that aims to study factors affecting the competency development of athletes to excellence and guidelines for the development of athletic performance to excellence Divided into 3 parts as follows;
 - Part 1: General information of interviewees. This is including Age, Education level, Current position, period of holding the position. Question characteristics are open-ended questions for interviewees to fill out their personal information.
 - Part 2: Comments on factors that affect the development of athletes' performance to excellence. A question characteristic is the main question line style, covering various issues according to the scope of research.
 - Part 3: Comments and suggestions about the way to develop athletes' performance excellence
2. Questionnaire for inquiring athletes by dividing into 3 parts as follows;
 - Part 1: General information of respondents, including gender, age, education level, occupation, income,

experience in sports competitions Question characteristics are closed-ended questions.

Part 2: Opinions about factors that affect the development of athletes' performance to excellence. It is a 5 level of Likert scale questionnaire with average scoring

criteria and interpretation of the grade level as shown in Table 1.

Part 3: Additional opinions and suggestions on ways to improve athletic performance towards excellence. Question characteristics are closed-ended questions.

Table 1 Interpretation and data analysis [6]

Score	Level Comments	Average score	Criteria for consideration
5	The most	4.51 – 5.00	the highest level of demand
4	Very	3.51 – 4.50	a high level of demand
3	Moderate	2.51 – 3.50	moderate needs
2	Less	1.51 – 2.50	a low level of need
1	The least	1.00 – 1.50	the least level of requirements

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

1. The investigators will analyze data from in-depth interviews by themselves. By means of recording and transcribing during verbatim type interviews Then provide the code and categorize the data Processing and summarizing facts.
2. For the analysis of data from the questionnaire, the researcher uses the main statistical descriptive processing method. By using the collected data to analyze statistical values.

V. RESULTS

The factors affecting the development of athletes' performance to excellence:

1. Factors affecting the development of athletes' ability to excellence in physical fitness are an element that indicates the success of athletes at every level and all types of sports.
2. Factor of Sports' skill and techniques are important factors for the development of athletes to excellence, especially learning sports skills and techniques from childhood.
3. Psychological factors are important components that are essential to the development of athletes towards excellence.
4. Guidelines for the development of all athletes' performance to excellence. It will be successful, having to work in the same direction.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study discovered the fact that increasing sport competences to be an important factor in the success of athlete development for excellence. Therefore, applying the competency concepts to help make the organization of sports-related organizations able to plan for considering who is suitable, what are their competency, whether how about talent or not. The organization must prepare competent people in accordance with the strategic planning of the organization.

The aspects' competency of sport is an important factor in the development of athletes to excellence. There are 3 important aspects: physical fitness, skills / techniques and mental fitness [11]. From the research, it is found that all 3 aspects should be developed in a consistent and appropriate manner in the same direction.

Sports skills / techniques are important factors for the development of athletes towards excellence [1]. From the research, it is found that to focus on the training of sports skills or techniques that are the basis of that sport regularly and in accordance with the sport type since childhood will make the children learn until they are proficient.

In term of psychology fitness, it was found that there are various elements can affect the mental state of the athletes while competing and practicing such as psychology strength, motivation, sports personality, and emotional aggression during sporting competition, anxiety and stress when encountering a competitor while competing or self-confidence, etc.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

1. Results from this study, the investigator got the factors that contribute to the development of athletes to excellence.
2. Results from this study will be concrete information for determining the guidelines for the development of athletes of the Sports Association of Thailand.
3. Psychological factors are important components that affect the mental state of athletes while practicing and competing.
4. Sports competence is important for the development of athletes. Therefore, should be collected data with other research tools.
5. There should be studies of empirical data on physical fitness, sport skills / techniques and absolute psychological competence to confirm the validity of the research and developed to be more complete.
6. There should be a study of factors affecting the development of athletes' competence to excellence in other.

REFERENCES

[1] A. Authchu, "Sports Competence.", Retrieved October 16, 2017 from ejournals.swu.ac.th/index.php/ENEDU/article/0072, 1993.

[2] A. Thipparuk, "Ways to develop Thai national football to be excellent in the next decade (2002-2012)"

- Master's thesis, Physical Education, The graduate school of Srinakharinwirot University, 2003.
- [3] B. Saiseenuan, C. Kertkam, M. Phiokram, P. Phiokram, "A study of motivation factors for being an athlete of sports institutions", Thailand National sport university Chumphon Campus, 2006.
- [4] D.C. McCieland, "Test for Competence, rather than Intelligence, American Psychologists." Vol. 17No. 7. P. 57-83, 1973.
- [5] D. Tianphut, "Cors Harman Cottipaternities: Competency factors for victory of business and people", Bangkok: Nagota Co., Ltd, 2003.
- [6] J. W. Best, "Research 19n Education", 4 th ed. New Jory: Pretbo-Hall, 1981.
- [7] Ministry of Tourism and Sports, "Strategic Plan for Creating Thai Sport to Excellence (2010 – 2016)", Bangkok: Permanent Secretary Ministry of Tourism and Sports, 2010.
- [8] Ministry of Tourism and Sports, "The sixth national sport development plan (2017-2021)", Bangkok: Permanent Secretary Ministry of Tourism and Sports, 2016.
- [9] N. Santhong, "Let's get to know competency", 1st published. Bangkok: H.R. Center, 2004.
- [10] R. Bunchan, "Research of the sports development plan for excellence", Bangkok: Sports Authority of Thailand, 2009.
- [11] S. Samahito, "Relaxation", Bangkok: Faculty of Sport Science, Kasetsart University, 1995

